

Several stiff-strawed, photoperiod-insensitive, high-yielding varieties have already been developed at CRRRI by crossing Japanese varieties such as Jikkoku, Hoyoku, and Shiranui with tall indicas. These lines show strong resistance to blast and fair resistance to bacterial blight under field conditions.

They have thin, erect leaves, late leaf senescence, and high harvest indices. At several testing centers in India, japonica-indica hybrids outyielded existing high-yielding varieties.

High and stable average yields in rice and wheat are obtained in Japan and several European countries without

adopting dwarf varieties. Efficient plant types suited to different agroclimatic conditions can be developed independent of the dwarf gene. But the process will not be simple, because a constellation of characters must be assembled through hybridization involving several parents with desired characters.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Variability in amylose content of rice

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An increasing demand for high-quality rices in both the domestic and foreign markets has brought close cooperation among rice breeders and cereal chemists. Amylose, the linear component of starch in nonwaxy rice, is responsible for the texture of cooked rice and is the chief influence on the eating quality judgments of milled rice. The nonwaxy varieties contain from about 7 to 34 percent amylose of milled rice (dry weight) or from 8 to 37 percent of starch. Rice varieties may be grouped on the basis of their amylose contents into waxy (1–2% amylose), low amylose (8–19%),

intermediate amylose (20–25%), or high amylose (more than 25%). The amylose content of a rice variety may vary by as much as 6 percentage points. Intermediate-amylose varieties remain soft even after cooling and are widely preferred in such countries as the Philippines, Indonesia, Vietnam, Burma, and Pakistan.

Because of the wide variability in amylose content within a variety, screening for intermediate-amylose types in a breeding program presents serious problems. A study was, therefore, undertaken to examine the sources and magnitude of variability due to several nonheritable factors. The total variability was classified into three main groups: that due to the environment or the conditions under which the plant grows;

that due to the sample plants or the method by which grain samples are obtained; and that due to the measurement technique or the variation involved in the laboratory. Varieties or selections differing in amylose content were selected to gain maximum information on how varieties interact with the various factors studied. The Simplified Amylose Procedure employing the Auto Analyzer Method was used to determine amylose content. The analysis of variance technique was used in most phases of the study.

Amylose content of grain, like protein content, was affected by environment. Temperature was negatively correlated with amylose in the low-amylose rice but showed no distinct trend in either the high- or the intermediate-amylose rices. Nitrogen application tended to reduce the amylose content of rice: split application caused greater reduction than basal application. The large effects of interaction between variety and location indicated that the relative performance of the rices varied from one location to another. The variation in amylose content among panicles of the same hill was larger than that among hills as well as among bulk-samples within a hill. Twenty grains and 100 mg of rice flour were found to be the optimum sample sizes for rice grain and for ground rice, respectively, in the determination of amylose content. Milled rice from a Test Tube Miller gave lower amylose values than did milled rice from a McGill Miller No. 2. The variance component due to samples was consistently much higher than that due to determinations of the same sample. The relative magnitudes of the variations due to runs and due to determinations within samples, on the other hand, were not consistent for all varieties.

Amylose content, which is a major factor influencing judgments of eating quality of milled rice, varies widely not only among rices, as above, but even within a variety. The differences in amylose content are reflected in varying textures of the rices when cooked.